

DSC and XRD Crystallinity Measurements for Carbon Fiber-reinforced Polyamide-6 Laminates Processed at Different Cooling Rates

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Questions? Remarks?
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Introduction

- Polyamide-6 (PA6) as an engineering thermoplastic, possess excellent mechanical properties, heat and chemical resistance.
- It has been extensively used in carbon-fiber (CF)-reinforced composites (CF/PA6) for various applications.
- Different mechanical properties can be obtained with semi-crystalline polymers depend on the crystallinity and different morphologies present in the matrix.
- The current work characterizes the crystallinity using different techniques: XRD and (modulated)-DSC.

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Problem statement

- Different processing techniques can induce different degree of crystallinity (DOC).
- The DOC highly depends on the cooling rate (CR).
- Due to the polymorphic nature of polyamides, specifically PA6, difficulties may arise in quantitatively interpreting the DSC and XRD results.

Incorrect and correct approaches for processing of PA6 DSC results

- Care should be taken when interpreting the DSC curves of PA6 and its composites:

Not to exclude the broad "silent crystallization" peak.

- Based on the thermal cycle, PA6 form α , γ , or metastable β crystalline phases.

- Less stable γ -crystals will transform to stable α phase during annealing below T_m .

Schematic ATP and autoclave consolidation process and associated crystallinity uniformity through the thickness

XRD pattern of (a) PA6 and CF/PA6 composites, (b) deconvoluted curves to find amorphous and crystalline structures.

Specimen preparation

- Thin CF/PA6 laminates are manufactured, maintaining a constant CR through the thickness of the plates:

Compression molding process able to induce four different CRs:

Temperature cycle of compression molding for laminates: fast cooling (P_CP) and moderate cooling (F_WC) rates.

Temperature cycle of compression molding for laminates: Very slow cooling rate (P_SC) and slow cooling (P_WC) rates.

Results and discussion

Produced laminates with four different cooling rates.

Plate	Cooling method	Avg. CR (°C/min)
P_SC	Convection by air [slow CR]	0.7
P_WC	Water cooling plates [moderate CR]	7.9
F_WC	Water cooling plates [moderate CR]	43
P_CP1	Cooling on plates at RT [fast CR]	770
P_CP2		

Typical XRD pattern of CF/PA6 after deconvolution of amorphous halo and crystalline structures.

DSC heat-cooling curves for F_WC and P_CP samples

mDSC result for P_CP distinguishes reversing and non-reversing heat flow

Effect of different CRs on Non-reversing heat flow from mDSC

□ Different phenomena are distinguished:

- Brill transition → initiates above T_g ,
- Sub-melting transition → before the main melting signal,
- Cold-crystallization → broad exothermic peak before melting, and
- Melting-recrystallization-remelting (MRR) of crystals → a shoulder before the melting peak temperature.

Conclusion

Resulting DOC of plates measured using (m)DSC and XRD techniques.

- Slow CR of 0.7 °C/min → Similar (m)DSC and XRD results
- Moderate to 7.9 to 43 °C/min → Lower crystallinity from XRD
- Fast CR of 770 °C/min → Much lower DOC from XRD
- At fast CR → imperfect β -crystals form
- Small and highly imperfect β -crystals form due to a high nucleation density and insufficient time for chain reorganization
- Presence of β -crystals → makes it hard to separate the diffraction peaks from the amorphous halo in XRD.

- ✓ XRD results are not accurate, specially at high CRs.
- ✓ Moisture in DSC-scanned samples lead to overestimated DOC.
- ✓ DSC heat flow curves hide possible exothermic crystallizations.
- ✓ mDSC analyses can give better understanding and results.